

I-CLAIM

**Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe**

Irregular migrants and precarity in the Dutch Food Delivery sector

Sector report

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Executive Summary

This research with food delivery workers with an irregular status in the Netherlands underscores the paradox of platform-based labour. While the job offers flexibility, immediate income and is an important part of the arrival infrastructure for newcomers who are looking to survive economically, the job also entrenches insecurity, dependency, precarity and high risks. It was found that the variety within people's legal status and the way the job is organized results in various levels of precarity for workers. The findings also highlight that migrant workers in the platform economy operate in an online-only, highly individualized labour structure with limited opportunities for collective action or worker solidarity making it difficult to change working condition violations.

The report is written at a time where the food delivery sector is increasingly regulated in the Netherlands, resulting in more precarity for those who cannot fulfil all the required requirements around regulations. The study outlines how work in the platform economy affects not only migrants' financial situations, but also their personal and family lives, as many workers are caught in a cycle of debt repayment that delays their ability to achieve social mobility or return to their home countries. Short and long term goals of workers differ depending on the life phase and the migration background as well as family situations.

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1. Introduction

The labour question in platform work has been the focus of much policy discussions, as well as labour activist work. Yet these discussions typically assume a national workforce and fail to recognize the interplay between the platform economy and migration regimes. The substantial share of migrants involved in platform work is however increasingly reflected in research (ILO 2021, van de Venne & van Roelen 2024), including food delivery work (Altenried 2024, van Doorn 2023, van Doorn et al. 2023, Gebrial 2024, Mendonca et al. 2023).

This report specifically focuses on exploring the complexities around irregular migrant workers within the food delivery sector in the Netherlands. It looks into how irregular migrant food delivery workers navigate precarious employment conditions while being shaped by their migration trajectory, their work circumstances, as well as their legal status. By examining the interplay between these factors, the research sheds light on the structural vulnerabilities that irregular migrant workers face in platform-based labour.

The fieldwork underneath this report allows us to look at both the actors and technologies involved, the procedural and exploitative dimensions, as well as the question how migrant workers themselves engage with and navigate the platform economy. We focus in particular on the complex relationship between food delivery's migration status, work conditions, and residence permits. It is based on 18 interviews with delivery workers, follow up interviews with 3 of these 18 workers and 6 expert interviews.

2. Context

2.1. Size of the food delivery sector in the Netherlands and type of workers

Numbers of the size of the food delivery sector in the Netherlands are not very accurate or up to date, but various sources prove it is a substantial part of the economy. Ter Weel et al. (2018) estimated that there are around 34.000 people employed in the platform economy in the Netherlands (0.4 % of the Dutch labour population) and that 1/3 of these are employed in food delivery which counts as around 10.000 people. Out of these 10.000 half of them work as employees and half are self-employed. The data comes from a survey that was done in 2017. It is to be expected that current numbers are higher because food delivery as a phenomena has increased tremendously after Covid.

The labour union, based on interviews with 100 food delivery workers in various cities in the Netherlands observed in 2019 that young people are overrepresented in the sector (FNV 2019). But that there is also a large share of older workers, even above 65, who work full time or more than that. There are delivery workers who are fully dependent for their income on this job. But there are also riders who do this type of work next to another job. The FNV representation of the workers is confirmed by an employee involved in the onboarding of food delivery workers for a platform we interviewed:

It is mainly men, 90% who we onboard. It is a lot of young people, students who just finished high school and want to earn some money. For many people it is their first job [...] And it is lots of people with a migration background, Moroccan, Turkish youth, but also from outside the EU, Bangladesh, Pakistan, and people from Portugal, Italians, Brazilians. It is a mix of everything actually (expert interview).

In student cities (Amsterdam, the Hague and Eindhoven) there is a large share of non-EU students doing food delivery work. These students are usually a bit older than Dutch students (Huijsmans 2025). In the Netherlands non-EU students are not allowed to work more than 16 hours a week next to their studies. But

this limitation does not count for freelance work which makes delivery work an appealing job for them. Paying the student fee, which is 10 times higher than for EU students, as well as high housing costs in the Netherlands, are important reasons for international students to work next to their studies. Some of them also provide for families abroad.

Apart from students not much is known about who the workers in this sector are. An employee involved in the onboarding for a platform we interviewed mentioned that they actively go to places where asylum seekers stay to recruit new 'talent' because they are always looking for new people.

'We went to Galaxy [a cruise ship where 1500 asylum seekers are housed] to see if people were interested to work for us. We gave a presentation what it is like to work for a food delivery platform. And there we did find quite a number of new talents who are now working for us [...] For some we had to apply for a work permit, that caused some problems but it also gave us something in return [...] the new law allows asylum seekers to work after 6 months so that is great' (expert interview).

Next to those who work on a student visa, there is thus workers who are in an asylum procedure. Since recently asylum seekers are allowed to work in the Netherlands. It is also known that there are workers in this sector whose asylum procedure has been rejected or whose visa is expired.

2.2. Food delivery platform providers in the Netherlands

Thuisbezorgd is the first and oldest platform for food delivery in the Netherlands. It was started by a Dutch student from Enschede in 2000 and has grown internationally. It still is the largest platform for food delivery in the Netherlands. At the start it worked with restaurants who had their own drivers but since 2016 Thuisbezorgd, like other platforms, has their own drivers. With Thuisbezorgd workers are hired through an employment agency. Drivers have to work certain weekend hours, and they need to indicate their working hours a few days in advance.

Deliveroo, a British company, started to be active in the Netherlands since 2015 and jumped in the niche of restaurants who at that time did not have their own drivers yet. In 2017 Deliveroo however announced that their workers had to be self-employed and register with the Dutch Chamber of Commerce (Kamer van Koophandel). Platform companies in general are real frontrunners in the deregularisation of labour (see also Mendonca et al. 2023). Working with independent contractors instead of employers is a means to reduce costs for the platforms and to circumvent labour laws. This announcement by Deliveroo triggered the installation of the Riders Union who took initiative to take Deliveroo to court (see below).

Uber Eats, an American company, is also active in the Netherlands since 2016. Next to these big players there are also smaller local platforms and restaurants who have their own drivers.

2.3. The Dutch court case against Deliveroo

On 24 March 2023, the Supreme Court in the Netherlands delivered a long-awaited ruling on the employment status of Deliveroo riders. Riders working for the app should be considered employees and therefore be entitled to workers' rights (Hoge Raad 2023). Earlier, the Amsterdam Court of Appeal had already decided that Deliveroo riders qualify as employees and Deliveroo's construction was described as 'bogus self-employment'. The Supreme Court confirmed that although the riders had a certain freedom to work whenever they wanted and to be replaced by someone else, all other circumstances lead to the conclusion that the riders are in fact employees. Coming to self-identify as an entrepreneur rather stems from the administrative practices that flows from the contested legal positioning as freelancer. This court case is victory for the trade union federation which has for years pressed to change and demanded

companies to employ the riders who work for them because there are concerns regarding employment conditions and possibilities for exploitation (FNV 2020; NLA 2022).

Deliveroo riders are since the court case entitled to employee rights like sickness pay and protection against dismissal. Deliveroo however responded to the court case by moving out of the country. Since November 2022 the platform Deliveroo is no longer active in the Netherlands. The court case did have implications for other platform companies operating in the Netherlands. Uber Eats has for example decided in 2024 to no longer work with self-employed drivers/freelancers. They hire their workers now through a staffing agency. Recently, the Tax Office in the Netherlands also announced to control stricter on pseudo self-employment more in general which might have played a role in Uber's decision as well. Uber was the last meal delivery firm in the Netherlands to still use self-employed riders. The switch means riders now have to register for work with the staffing agency. For Uber taxi drivers there is similar concerns, but so far Uber is still employing them as self-employed workers although a court case on this is still pending.

3. Methodology

The data underneath this report was collected in Utrecht over a six-month period, from December 2024 to April 2025 by a postdoctoral researcher and three community researchers. Most interviews took about an hour and were conducted in people's home or semi-public spaces. Some interviews were shorter and during working hours which meant outside in the streets. Most interviews were conducted in English and in Portuguese. A Dutch, Nigerian and Brazilian community researcher were hired on the project to support data collection. They facilitated contact with participants and made it possible to do interviews in people's native language.

Only male delivery workers were interviewed from a variety of countries (see appendix 1 for the complete overview of respondents). 3 follow up interviews were conducted with delivery workers. These follow up interviews employed an object based methodology where we talked more in-depth about everyday life issues guided by objects participants brought along to the interview. All interviewees consented to having their interviews recorded. As a form of remuneration for their participation, the migrant workers received a €15 voucher for a local supermarket.

4. Results from fieldwork

The main findings of this research highlights how different migration backgrounds and statuses impact on the precarious position of migrant workers within food delivery work. We focus on how delivery work as a job is embedded in the arrival infrastructures for irregular migrants looking for work, how people get access to the job, how the sector shapes irregular migrant's working conditions in different ways and what options there are in terms of claiming labour rights for irregular workers in this sector.

4.1. Delivery Work as part of Arrival Infrastructures

The literature on "arrival infrastructures" fits the experiences of finding work for irregular migrants very well. Arrival infrastructures constitute the "parts of the urban fabric within which newcomers become entangled on arrival, and where their future local or translocal social mobilities are produced as much as negotiated" (Meeus et al., 2019). The apps provide access to work and friends alert people to these jobs. Gig platforms and app-based work can as such contribute significantly to our understanding of the range and nature of

urban arrival infrastructures, particularly with respect to low-wage labour markets and how these are becoming increasingly mediated by apps.

If you don't have access to the formal labour market because of visa related reasons, delivery work seems a good alternative. It can be seen as an entry point into the labour market for migrants struggling with stratified labour markets requesting language skills, documents, qualifications (see also Altenried 2024). At first sight it seems easy in terms of access, although even for this job some people say it is hard when you are new to the city and you don't speak the language. The job does not involve too much communication but there is communication with restaurant owners and with clients to a certain extent. Quite a few delivery workers reported it took some time before they got the contacts to start this job but also time before they felt comfortable enough in the city to find their way around. In the beginning you don't know the city plan, you might not be so handy with biking. And you need to know the city when you do this type of work. A 25-year-old Nigerian worker for example explained:

“This work was not possible when I just arrived in Utrecht as I did not know the city at all”

Platform work such as food delivery has proven to be readily accommodating to migrants looking for a quick income stream. The advantage of this job is that you can start immediately and there are no limits on hours you are allowed to work. Nearly all our interviewees found it relatively easy to sign up with platform companies and could usually start working straight away. There is inequality however in access, even to these types of jobs. It is easier for some and more complicated for others as the ability to find some measure of stability upon arrival depends on the uneven accessibility of existing resources (see also Felder et al., 2020). Whether you can trust and rely on your intermediary or not also makes a difference, as well as the number of intermediaries you are dependent on.

4.2. Access to the job and onboarding

Location-based platform work in general is appealing to migrants. The quick and automated onboarding process largely eliminates hurdles like language barriers, legal restrictions, discrimination in the selection procedure, or a lack of formal qualifications (Hampel & Krause 2023). Entering a platform does not require lengthy culturally particular and at times discriminatory job application processes. Most of the time you are asked to fill in a short online registration form available in English. Although onboarding procedures are currently changing in the Netherlands, platform work is still characterized by a more-or-less-anonymous employment relationship, where the employee interacts with an app rather than a line manager. For irregular migrants it is one of the few sectors where it is easier to circumvent obstacles to formal work.

When we asked people why they decided to do this job it was pointed out that there is a lack of opportunities for irregular migrants to work in the Netherlands. There are not so many jobs available to them because there is identity checks in most jobs and a language barrier. Most often riders are hired through acquaintances who already work as riders or through co-nationals, or other intermediaries who rent out accounts. Social media (Facebook, WhatsApp groups) plays an important role in matchmaking as well. A 31 year man from Algeria who worked as a delivery worker explained to us how he sees this system:

“The first thing you have to do is look for lazy people. If you find lazy people, they will give you the account, or make an account for you to work, they then take 40%. Yeah. Yeah, because they are lazy, you know, that's, uh. And then you do the work. It is lazy and greedy people who you rely on” (interview number 8).

Through our fieldwork we came across many stories of people who did not get paid for the work they did because they were dependent on other people's account. A 20-year-old Nigerian man we interviewed for example explained that he worked on somebody's account as a delivery worker and was promised to get paid, but that never happened.

"I worked for 2 months and they did not pay me. Nothing." (interview number 11)

Similar things happened to many other of our respondents. A 25-year-old Nigerian delivery worker illustrated the unfairness related to how payment in this sector sometimes goes and the amount of intermediaries that can be involved in between you doing the job and the person who receives the salary for that job.

"The work, it paid me, but not, uh, I don't know if it was fair because, uh, according to my friends, what they were given was fair to them. So I always go with them because I was an ignorant man. Yeah. So only when you are a newcomer to a place, because it was somebody owns the app. I was, uh, I was working for somebody. Yeah. And I told him he would tell me do like this because I was not allowed to have, uh, the bike. It's not that you will come there. They will just give you the bike. You don't have an address. You don't have a home. So before they give you that, you must have some city requirements like address of a place where they can find you if the bike is missing. So I don't have such a place. It was somebody, I passed through the hands of three people before they get to the owner of the app [...]. he paid percentage to 3 people that leave me with them. So I was only given a little." (interview number 9)

Not getting paid, or getting paid less is a serious risk for irregular workers (see also Fairwork 2025). When you need to rely on other people's accounts the risk increases. The owner of the account can also stop the account without informing the person working on the account, having control over whether people can actually work or not. A Nigerian man we interviewed said:

"My account got blocked, I cannot work right now because it is blocked and I don't know why it is blocked". (interview number 13)

Accounts also get blocked after consumers have filled complaints. Riders do not always get informed about this.

Since 2024 there is a new way of working with Uber in the Netherlands which now hires people only through a staffing agency. This makes it harder for undocumented migrants to perform this type of work. Already people were experiencing higher prices to rent somebody else's account. The new situation will most likely increase the risks for irregular migrants performing this type of work as one rider explained:

"If uber eats stops, it will be difficult for us to work, it was easy to start the work but now they have stopped my account". (interview number 15)

An expert we interviewed explained to us that the transition is not easy on the supply side. Officially since 1st of January 2025 all accounts need to be transferred but in practice it takes longer.

"We did not transfer all accounts at the same time, because that is impossible. We take it step by step. And there is the issue that people want to keep their account, with their reviews, because when you need to start all over and you already had a history of 1000 orders that is a problem. We are working on that". (expert interview)

The onboarding is a whole procedure that actually involves many checks making the sector less accessible for some workers.

“If people are blacklisted because there was fraud involved in their previous account, if they have failed to deliver, or they did not confirm with the rules, then that is stopped. We also always call people for a quick check, do they speak Dutch or English and we ask which mode of transport they want to use. We don’t do cars and we sometimes need to explain that. If all is fine we can start the onboarding after an ID check, bank accounts and then the ANP group will pay a visit to people’s home address for another ID check. They check if the person who subscribed is the person who lives there. And then they can start their first shift.” (expert interview)

4.3. Working Conditions in the sector

The flexible nature of delivery jobs is appealing to many migrants and for some workers it works out well. A 32-year-old Brazilian delivery worker who has two children and a grandchild in Brazil and works in the Netherlands explains:

“Delivery is how I made the most money, where I managed to change my life, my family’s life, thank God. (...) I always set myself targets and beat them, like 1,000 and 1,200 euro a week.” (interview number 6)

Next to flexibility and opportunities to earn a lot, there is also precarity. Delivery drivers only get paid when they deliver, not when they for example wait for the next order. The job however typically involves quite a lot of waiting at restaurants and for new orders. But this time in between gigs is not paid, it is unpaid time in the system. Moreover, paying for the gig (order delivered) only also means no contribution is made to any social provisioning (sick leave coverage, pensions) shifting the costs of social reproduction on the riders. The physicality of the job is also wearing people out.

A 31 year old Algerian man used the metaphor of slavery to describe the working conditions in the delivery work sector for undocumented migrants.

“The free work. It’s the only real work. All the other work is. It’s like a, it’s, uh, slaves work. Yeah. I will tell you something. Work in six days, rest one day, 11 months to work, one month to rest, one month? Working all my life to, uh, to rest. So slave. You are a slave. Hello. But the problem with slaves: they will think you are not slaves. That’s the problem. That’s the bad. That’s the bad of slaves. In the past, the slaves were fighting to be free. But now, the slaves think they are free. So they are slaves with a tall rope. At least we jump rope (laughs), but at the end of the day we are enslaved”. (interview number 8)

Risks involved in the sector are that delivery workers often work long hours and are under extreme pressure to ride fast so they can take more orders. The work process consists of logging in the app, by which the shift officially starts, and through which working hours are counted. Once logged in riders receive order numbers with instruction for pick-up and delivery routes. There is no possibility for rejecting orders in case riders fear ways are too long and bike batteries are low. Many respondents told us that the system makes you feel you always need to go faster.

Many migrant riders also complain about restaurants letting them wait for long which delays their delivery, but above all makes them lose time to get more orders. Most of the companies claim to provide migrants with bags, jackets, rain trousers, helmets and gloves. Many migrant workers however take it upon

themselves to buy clothes and to buy, lease or rent (better quality) bicycles. This additional financial burden further strains their already limited income. In almost all interviews, migrant workers reported the use of their personal mobile phones and data.

Being out and about in the city all the time is also an important part of the working conditions. Many workers complain about the weather. You have to drive through heavy rain and snow.

“The delivery work is so stressful and we are facing a lot of cold. Sometimes you stand in the cold, for so many hours before you make 20 euro. You stand in the cold. And the cold will be going in your head if you don't cover up”. (interview 13)

All these working conditions impact on riders' safety and it also increases the risk of traffic incidents. The Radical Riders' Union has published a number of riders' stories concerning serious injuries due to traffic accidents. Riders who are the most marginalised are often also the most affected by the lack of employment rights. There are examples of reports on riders who have become homeless when they were unable to continue working due to a broken leg sustained on the job (Rengers & Bronzwaer 2022).

4.4. Labour Rights and Unionizing

Even though the union has played a huge role in regulating the sector, irregular migrants are highly unaware of their working rights in this sector in the Netherlands. Delivery workers often assume it is normal they are not paid when they are on sick leave or holiday, although minimum wage must be paid out. There is always the risk that their account will be closed in case of a problem, complaint. Hence, many ride faster and do not report accidents or take sick leave or holidays when needed. The biggest labour right violation we came across during our fieldwork is that people don't get paid for the work they are performing (see also Fairwork 2025).

Another factor contributing to their vulnerability is the absence of a physical space where migrant workers can interact with company managers or colleagues, as most processes are conducted exclusively online. This lack of a physical workspace not only makes it difficult for workers to forge connections or build networks but also reinforces the highly individualized nature of the economy, leaving workers isolated and without collective support. People told us it was also very difficult to reach the online platform (Discord) in case there were for example technical issues or people wanted to complain. Not being able to speak to a person makes them feel even less connected and cared for as employees. In case of traffic accidents, or rude behaviour by customers there is no place where riders can complain. There are no procedures in place and complaining might even impact the orders you get and as such the money you can earn.

4.5. Impact of Doing Delivery work on everyday life

For some respondents doing delivery work is a good way to earn money. Like a 46-year-old Brazilian delivery worker we interviewed who already in Brazil worked as an Uber taxi driver but could not earn enough money there.

“Here I'm managing to pay for my son's university fees, I am paying them more than I used to be able to do. So I'm looking after them very well and that is because of this job”. (interview number 5)

At the same time delivery work is also a job people do not want to do for long. Some riders described doing the job as being *'stuck in a system that you know is not good for you'*. The system rushes you and makes you go faster and faster which has implications on your health. Working irregular hours also makes it difficult to sustain a social and family life. Flexible working hours meant that some people we interviewed had other jobs in the morning and afternoon and did delivery work in the evening/night. Some combined it with parenting. Research shows that delivery riders with families and care obligations on the other hand are less involved in risky behaviour, also described as a certain type of 'machismo' that genders the occupation (Timko & van Melik 2021).

Interviews reveal that doing delivery work can obstruct upward mobility. A 24-year-old Nigerian man who attends a special university program for irregular migrants for example explained how he sees the job compared to how others see it:

"Because for me, my goal is not to do delivery. Some of them their goal is to just do delivery. They want to just do delivery and earn money. But for me it's different. I want to invest in life". (interview number 10)

Doing delivery work is often seen as a job where you don't need to speak the language. But not speaking the language and not learning the language might also result in serious sentiments of isolation. Like a 23-year-old male Brazilian worker who explained during an interview that he feels so lonely that he is seriously considering to go back to Brazil now.

"I can't communicate with anyone. (...) I go to places and I feel like an empty guy, with nothing, like nobody. Like it's that thing over there. I can't talk to people, they just can't understand me." (interview number 7)

Interviews also pointed out that the precarity associated with gig work intersects with prior experiences of vulnerability and insecurity that goes beyond the platform labour context. A 26-year-old Egyptian delivery worker illustrated this very powerful.

"Without documents everything is hard bro. Not just the work. Everything. Not just the work. Everything. When you don't have a document, like you don't have anything. Yeah." (interview number 12)

5. Conclusion

As a result of lack of employment opportunities in the formal economy, many irregular migrants are dependent on the platform economy such as food delivery work that offers opportunities to earn immediate income. Delivery work is a job performed by a wide variety of people, including migrants with irregular status for whom the earned income is an important way to survive.

Next to an economic opportunity it was found that delivery work easily becomes cruel when the physicality of the work is for example wearing you out. All irregular workers in the sector suffer from unhealthy and unsafe working conditions, a lack of job security and the possibility of termination or receiving an official warning with little recourse which puts them in a precarious situation. For those working on other people's accounts there is the risk of not being paid for the work that is done. Being stuck in a vicious circle of working long hours and earning little might also obstruct materializing future dreams and can frustrate longer term aspirations.

Precarity in the food delivery sector is produced both by the characteristics of the sector, as well as by the variety in people's legal status. Many of the Brazilian delivery workers we interviewed have Portuguese citizenship, or are in the procedure of getting it. This does not mean they are allowed to work in the Netherlands, but it does give them more stability, freedom and control over the situation compared to those without EU citizenship. Non-EU students who work to fund their studies and/or to provide for families overseas are legally in a better position than for example rejected asylum seekers whose exposure to authorities might result in detention or even deportations. The visibility of the job makes people in more precarious legal situations even more precarious.

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Appendix

Overview interviews with delivery workers in the Netherlands						
1	Brazil	Male	34	Married, no children, wife in NL	2,5 years in NL	Brazilian citizenship
2	Brazil	Male	23	Single, shares room with friend	11 months in NL	Overstayed tourist visa
3	Brazil	Male	19	Single, lives with brother who recently got EU citizenship, mother in Portugal	7 months in NL (6 years in Portugal)	Residence permit in Portugal, in procedure Portuguese citizenship
4	Brazil	Male	24	In relationship, his girlfriend is also from Brazil and undocumented	1 year and 3 months in NL (from age 5-14 he lived undocumented in NL, after that in Portugal)	In procedure Portuguese citizenship
5	Brazil	Male	46	Adult children in Brazil, lives in shared flat, has girlfriend in NL	3 years in NL	In procedure Portuguese citizenship
6	Brazil	Male	32	He lives with his brother in NL, his girlfriend went back to Brazil. He sends money to his 2 children and his mother in Brazil. He also has 1 grandchild in Brazil	1 year and 5 months	Overstayed his tourist visa
7	Brazil	Male	23	Lives with brother, also undocumented	1 year	Overstayed tourist visa
8	Algeria	Male	31	Single	4 years in NL	He didn't apply for asylum because he knew he wouldn't make it
9	Nigerian	Male	25	Nephew in NL, family in Nigeria	6 years in NL (since 2019)	
10	Nigerian	Male	24	2 sisters, 1 brother, 1 mother in Nigeria	8 years in NL	Rejected asylum seeker

11	Nigerian	Male	20	Single, born in NL, then back to Nigeria, came on his own to NL after his mom and granddad died	2 years in NL	Rejected asylum seeker living in a shelter
12	Egypt	Male	26	Single	6 years in NL	Back in procedure after Dublin but rejected
13	Nigeria	Male	38	Single	6 years in NL	Rejected asylum seeker
14	Morocco	Male	22	Single, father passed away in Morocco and not good relationship with mother	6 years in NL	Rejected asylum seeker
15	Bangladesh	Male	23	Single, came on his own	4 months	Student visa
16	South Africa	Male	30	Single, worked for Uber in South Africa too	1 year	In asylum procedure
17	Turkish	Male	26	Single	2 years	Romanian passport
18	Bangladesh	Male	24	Single	8 maanden	Student visa

Object based follow up interviews delivery workers

1	Algeria	(follow up interview 8)
2	Egypt	(follow up interview 12)
3	Nigeria	(follow up interview 13)

Expert interviews for delivery work sector in the Netherlands

1	Brazilian community leader
2	Brazilian vice consul
3	Policymaker city of Utrecht
4	NGO Utrecht
5	NGO Utrecht
6	Employment agency involved in onboarding for delivery work

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—REALIZZA IL CAMBIAMENTO—

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